

ChiSA: Static Analysis for Lightweight Chisel Verification

(Supplementary Material)

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This supplementary material presents additional details omitted from the main paper due to space constraints. It includes the specification of ChAIR (Section 1) and presents complete proofs for key theoretical results whose proof sketches in the main text require further elaboration (Section 2).

CCS Concepts: • **Theory of computation** → **Program analysis**; • **Hardware** → **Hardware description languages and compilation**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Static Analysis, Hardware, Chisel

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1 Specification of ChAIR

ChAIR (Chisel-specific Intermediate Representation for Analysis) is a linear intermediate representation (IR) based on three-address code (3AC), which simplifies the construction of static analyses [7]. Unlike Firrtl [1]—the official Chisel compiler IR—and its related CIRCT [3] dialects, all of which adopt a recursive IR structure based on either abstract syntax trees (ASTs) or MLIR [4] operations and are primarily designed for transformation and lowering tasks, ChAIR adopts a flat, analyzable structure better suited for static analysis. It also employs static single assignment (SSA) form, aligning with the intrinsic structure of hardware designs (as discussed in Section 2.2 of the main paper) and enabling efficient sparse analysis [9].

We begin by introducing the core classes in ChAIR that abstract key language constructs of Chisel (Section 1.1). To preserve anonymity, we omit organization-specific prefixes when referencing classes and packages (shown in purple) from the ChiSA project. We then present the 3AC grammar for expressions (Section 1.2) and statements (Section 1.3) in ChAIR. Additional details about APIs provided by ChAIR to facilitate static analysis development are available in the documentation accompanying the ChiSA project.

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1.1 Core Classes

- **Circuit** (in package `ir`) serves as the entry point of ChAIR, representing an entire circuit design. A circuit consists of multiple reusable modules, one of which is designated as the top module. The name of the circuit is defined by the name of this top module.
- **Module** (in package `ir`) represents a reusable hardware block that can be instantiated multiple times. Each module contains various pieces of information, including its name, member declarations (variables, submodule instances, memories), and native metadata (for inaccessible external definitions).
- **Type** (in package `ir.type`) represents the type system in ChAIR. It includes several subclasses for both data and control types:
 - **UIntType** and **SIntType** represent fixed-width unsigned and signed integers, respectively.
 - **ClockType** represents clock signals that synchronize the behavior of registers and memories.
 - **AsyncResetType** represents signals used to asynchronously reset register values, temporarily overriding clock-driven synchronization.
- **Var** (in package `ir.expr`) represents variables within a module that correspond to circuit locations holding values. It has several subclasses, each capturing different value-updating semantics:
 - **Ports** represent a module's interface used to communicate with other modules.
 - **Wire** models a circuit component that reactively propagates values but does not retain state.
 - **Reg** models a state-holding component that remembers its value across clock cycles. Its updates are synchronized by an associated clock signal. Special registers may include asynchronous reset logic, allowing them to reset independently of clock synchronization.
 - **Memory.Cell** represents the abstract location in the memory that stores values. The semantics of value updates for a memory cell are determined by the memory to which it belongs.
- **Memory** (in package `ir`) provides an abstract representation of a hardware memory in ChAIR. A memory is characterized by the following components:
 - (1) A data type that specifies the type of each memory element, and a positive integer denoting the total number of elements.
 - (2) A variable number of named **MemoryAccessor**'s (in package `ir`), each associated with an **AccessorKind** (in package `ir.memory`) such as `reader`, `writer`, or `readwriter`. The precise semantics of these accessors are detailed in ChiSA's documentation.
 - (3) A non-negative integer representing the read latency—i.e., the number of clock cycles between setting a read address and observing the corresponding data value at the read port.
 - (4) A positive integer representing the write latency—i.e., the number of clock cycles between setting a write address and data, and the point at which the written value is committed to the memory.
 - (5) A **ReadUnderWrite** (in package `ir.memory`) flag, which can take values such as `old`, `new`, or `undefined`, specifying the memory's behavior when a location is read and written concurrently. The precise semantics of each flag are documented in the ChiSA's documentation.
- **Native** (in package `ir`) represents native metadata, such as intellectual property (IP) core parameters. It is used exclusively in external modules whose internal definitions are inaccessible.

- **Attribute** (in package `ir.attribute`) conveys additional metadata from the Chisel frontend to ChAIR, such as source locations and annotations that encode designer intentions. It also provides an extensible interface for enriching the semantic information in ChAIR.
- **Exp** (in package `ir.expr`) represents expressions, and **Stmt** (in package `ir.stmt`) represents statements. Both include a rich suite of subclasses that comprehensively cover Chisel language features. Due to the large number of variants, we do not enumerate all expressions and statements here. Instead, we provide their grammar in Section 1.2 (for **Exp**) and Section 1.3 (for **Stmt**). Full semantic and implementation details can be found in the well-documented source code of ChiSA.

All the aforementioned classes are thoughtfully designed with rich, well-documented, and user-friendly APIs to streamline the development of Chisel static analyses using ChiSA. These resources are available in the open-source ChiSA repository.

1.2 Grammar of Expressions

In the grammar presented below, *identifier* denotes identifiers, *integer* denotes integer literals, and *string* denotes text strings. For readability, all non-terminal symbols are typeset in italics, and all terminal symbols are rendered in red.

$$\text{Exp} \rightarrow \text{Var} \mid \text{Value} \mid \text{Access} \mid \text{MuxExp} \mid \text{UnaryExp} \mid \text{BinaryExp}$$

- $\text{Var} \rightarrow \text{Identifier}$
- $\text{Value} \rightarrow \text{UInt}<\text{Integer}>(\text{Integer}) \mid \text{SInt}<\text{Integer}>(\text{Integer})$
- $\text{Access} \rightarrow \text{PortAccess} \mid \text{MemAccess}$
 - $\text{PortAccess} \rightarrow \text{ModuleInstance}.\text{Port}$
 - * $\text{ModuleInstance} \rightarrow \text{Identifier}$
 - * $\text{Port} \rightarrow \text{Identifier}$
 - $\text{MemAccess} \rightarrow \text{Memory}.\text{MemoryAccessor}.\text{Field}$
 - * $\text{Memory} \rightarrow \text{Identifier}$
 - * $\text{MemoryAccessor} \rightarrow \text{Identifier}$
 - * $\text{Field} \rightarrow \text{clk} \mid \text{en} \mid \text{addr} \mid \text{data} \mid \text{mask} \mid \text{rdata} \mid \text{wmode} \mid \text{wdata} \mid \text{wmask}$
- $\text{MuxExp} \rightarrow \text{mux}(\text{Var}, \text{Var}, \text{Var})$
- $\text{UnaryExp} \rightarrow \text{CastExp} \mid \text{NegExp} \mid \text{NotExp} \mid \text{ReductionExp} \mid \text{ResizeExp} \mid \text{BitsExp}$
 - $\text{CastExp} \rightarrow \text{CastOp}(\text{Var})$
 - * $\text{CastOp} \rightarrow \text{asUInt} \mid \text{asSInt} \mid \text{asClock} \mid \text{asAsyncReset} \mid \text{cvt}$
 - $\text{NegExp} \rightarrow \text{neg}(\text{Var})$
 - $\text{NotExp} \rightarrow \text{not}(\text{Var})$
 - $\text{ReductionExp} \rightarrow \text{ReductionOp}(\text{Var})$
 - * $\text{ReductionOp} \rightarrow \text{andr} \mid \text{orr} \mid \text{xorr}$
 - $\text{ResizeExp} \rightarrow \text{ResizeOp}(\text{Var}, \text{Integer})$
 - * $\text{ResizeOp} \rightarrow \text{pad} \mid \text{shl} \mid \text{shr} \mid \text{head} \mid \text{tail}$
 - $\text{BitsExp} \rightarrow \text{bits}(\text{Var}, \text{Integer}, \text{Integer})$
- $\text{BinaryExp} \rightarrow \text{ArithmeticExp} \mid \text{ComparisonExp} \mid \text{DynamicShiftExp} \mid \text{BitwiseExp}$

- $ArithmeticExp \rightarrow ArithmeticOp(Var, Var)$
 - * $ArithmeticOp \rightarrow add \mid sub \mid mul \mid div \mid rem$
- $ComparisonExp \rightarrow ComparisonOp(Var, Var)$
 - * $ComparisonOp \rightarrow lt \mid leq \mid gt \mid geq \mid eq \mid neq$
- $DynamicShiftExp \rightarrow DynamicShiftOp(Var, Var)$
 - * $DynamicShiftOp \rightarrow dshl \mid dshr$
- $BitwiseExp \rightarrow BitwiseOp(Var, Var)$
 - * $BitwiseOp \rightarrow and \mid or \mid xor \mid cat$

1.3 Grammar of Statements

$Stmt \rightarrow ConnectStmt \mid MonitorStmt$

- $ConnectStmt \rightarrow Const \mid LoadPort \mid StorePort \mid LoadMem \mid StoreMem \mid Mux \mid Unary \mid Binary$
 - $Const \rightarrow Var := Value$
 - $Copy \rightarrow Var := Var$
 - $LoadPort \rightarrow Var := PortAccess$
 - $StorePort \rightarrow PortAccess := Var$
 - $LoadMem \rightarrow Var := MemAccess$
 - $StoreMem \rightarrow MemAccess := Var$
 - $Mux \rightarrow Var := MuxExp$
 - $Unary \rightarrow Var := UnaryExp$
 - $Binary \rightarrow Var := BinaryExp$
- $MonitorStmt \rightarrow Printf \mid Stop \mid VerificationStmt$
 - $Printf \rightarrow printf(Var, Var, String, Var^*)$
 - $Stop \rightarrow stop(Var, Var, Integer)$
 - $VerificationStmt \rightarrow VerificationPrimitive(Var, Var, Var, String)$
 - * $VerificationPrimitive \rightarrow assert \mid assume \mid cover$

2 Detailed Proofs of Properties in Main Paper

Due to space constraints and to aid readability, the main paper includes only proof sketches for key results. This section provides the full versions of those proofs, along with additional formal discussions and elaborations where appropriate.

2.1 Proofs of Properties in Section 2

We begin by recalling the first two theorems from Section 2 of the main paper. Since their proof sketches are already sufficiently detailed to constitute complete proofs, we do not repeat them here for brevity.

THEOREM 2.1 (ORIGINAL THEOREM 2.1 IN OUR PAPER). *A circuit could oscillate even if only a finite sequence of external stimuli is applied:*

$$\exists c \in \text{Circuit}. \exists c \in \text{Config}_C. \exists \text{an infinite reduction sequence from } c.$$

THEOREM 2.2 (ORIGINAL THEOREM 2.2 IN OUR PAPER). *A circuit without a combinational loop cannot oscillate:*

If C contains no combinational loop, then \nexists infinite reduction sequence from any $c \in \mathbf{Config}_C$.

In this subsection, we prove Theorem 2.3 from our main paper, which establishes that the final environment produced by any reduction sequence from the same initial configuration is deterministic. In fact, we prove a stronger proposition concerning stability (Lemma 2.7), from which Theorem 2.3 follows as a corollary. To facilitate this, we introduce a new definition along with several prerequisite lemmas.

Definition 2.3. For a configuration $\langle S, E, I \rangle$ of a circuit C without combinational loops, if $E(x) = \llbracket e \rrbracket_E$ holds for any $x = e \in C_- - I$, we call the configuration *legal*.

The initial configuration $c_0 = \langle S, E_{\text{rand}}, C_- \rangle$ is legal since $C_- - C_- = \emptyset$.

LEMMA 2.4. *If $\langle S, E, I \rangle$ is a legal configuration of a circuit C without combinational loops and $C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$, $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ is also legal.*

PROOF. Do case analysis on $C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$:

- (1) Case S-POKE: In this case, $I = \emptyset, I' = \mathcal{A}_C(E, E')$. For any $x = e \in C_- - I'$, any $v \in \text{Use}(x = e)$ satisfies $E(v) = E'(v)$ since $x = e$ will be in $\mathcal{A}_C(E, E') = I'$ otherwise. Therefore,

$$\llbracket e \rrbracket_{E'} = \llbracket e \rrbracket_E = E(x).$$

Since x is not poked in this step (because x is not an input), $E(x) = E'(x)$. It follows that $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ is legal.

- (2) Case S-TICK: Similar.

- (3) Case C-EVAL: Suppose the item ι used in this step is $x = e$. Since C has no combinational loop, $x \notin \text{Use}(x = e)$ holds and thus $E'(x) = \llbracket e \rrbracket_{E'}$.

If $E(x) = E'(x)$, it deduces that $I' = I - \{x = e\}$ and $E = E'$. Therefore, any $x' = e' \in C_- - I' = (C_- - I) \cup \{x = e\}$ is either identical to $x = e$ or in $C_- - I$. The former case is trivial. For the latter case, $\llbracket e' \rrbracket_{E'} = \llbracket e' \rrbracket_E = E(x') = E'(x')$.

If $E(x) \neq E'(x)$, $C_- - I' = C_- - (I - \{x = e\}) - \mathcal{A}_C(E, E')$, where $\mathcal{A}_C(E, E') = \text{Succ}(x = e)$. In this case, any $x' = e' \in C_- - I'$ which is not identical to $x = e$ is in $C_- - I$ and not in $\text{Succ}(x = e)$, whence $x \notin \text{Use}(x' = e')$. Since E and E' only differ in x , $\llbracket e' \rrbracket_{E'} = \llbracket e' \rrbracket_E = E(x') = E'(x')$. □

COROLLARY 2.5. *Given a legal configuration $\langle S, E, I \rangle$ a circuit C without combinational loops, $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ is legal if $C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle$.*

PROOF. Trivial induction. □

LEMMA 2.6 (LOCAL CONFLUENCE). *For a legal configuration $\langle S, E, I \rangle$ of a circuit C without combinational loops, if $C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \wedge C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle$, there exists $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ such that $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle \wedge \langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle$.*

PROOF. Do a case analysis on I :

- (1) If $I = \emptyset$, only S-POKE or S-TICK can be used to make progress. The choice is determined by the first element of S , so $S_1 = S_2 \wedge E_1 = E_2 \wedge I_1 = I_2$. Let $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ be $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle$.
- (2) If $I \neq \emptyset$, only C-EVAL can be used to make progress. Assume that:

$$C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S, E[x_1 \mapsto v_1], I'_1 \cup A_1 \rangle = \langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle,$$

$$C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S, E[x_2 \mapsto v_2], I'_2 \cup A_2 \rangle = \langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle,$$

where:

- $v_1 = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_E$, $A_1 = \mathcal{A}_C(E, E[x_1 \mapsto v_1])$, $I'_1 = I - \{x_1 = e_1\}$;
- $v_2 = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_E$, $A_2 = \mathcal{A}_C(E, E[x_2 \mapsto v_2])$, $I'_2 = I - \{x_2 = e_2\}$.

The case when $x_1 = e_1$ is identical with $x_2 = e_2$ is trivial, so we assume that the two items are not identical. Since C has no combinational loop, it is impossible that $x_1 \in \text{Use}(x_2 = e_2) \wedge x_2 \in \text{Use}(x_1 = e_1)$. Therefore, we could do a case analysis on their use-relation:

- (a) If $x_1 \notin \text{Use}(x_2 = e_2) \wedge x_2 \notin \text{Use}(x_1 = e_1)$, let:

$$\begin{aligned} E' &= E[x_1 \mapsto v_1][x_2 \mapsto v_2], \\ I' &= (I - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A_1 \cup A_2. \end{aligned}$$

It follows immediately that $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$ and $\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$.

- (b) If $x_1 \in \text{Use}(x_2 = e_2) \wedge x_2 \notin \text{Use}(x_1 = e_1)$, let $v'_2 = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{E[x_1 \mapsto v_1]}$, $A'_2 = \mathcal{A}_C(E[x_1 \mapsto v_1], E[x_1 \mapsto v_1][x_2 \mapsto v'_2])$ and:

$$\begin{aligned} E' &= E[x_1 \mapsto v_1][x_2 \mapsto v'_2], \\ I' &= (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A'_2. \end{aligned}$$

It immediately deduces that $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$. As for another configuration $\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle$, we have $\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1], (I_2 - \{x_1 = e_1\}) \cup \mathcal{A}_C(E_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1]) \rangle$. A further case analysis is needed:

- (i) Case $v_1 = E_2(x_1)$: it follows that $E(x_1) = E_2(x_1) = v_1$, whence $\mathcal{A}_C(E_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1]) = A_1 = \emptyset$. Therefore, we have $E = E_1$ and $v'_2 = v_2$, whence $A_2 = A'_2$. It deduces that $E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1] = E_2 = E[x_2 \mapsto v_2] = E[x_2 \mapsto v'_2] = E[x_1 \mapsto v_1][x_2 \mapsto v'_2] = E'$ and $(I_2 - \{x_1 = e_1\}) \cup \mathcal{A}_C(E_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1]) = I_2 - \{x_1 = e_1\} = (I - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A'_2 = I'$. So $\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S', E', I' \rangle$.
- (ii) Case $v_1 \neq E_2(x_1)$: in this case $A'_1 = \mathcal{A}_C(E_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1]) = \text{Succ}(x_1 = e_1) \cap C_- = A_1$ is not empty. Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \\ &\rightsquigarrow \langle S_2, E_2[x_1 \mapsto v_1], (I_2 - \{x_1 = e_1\}) \cup A'_1 \rangle \\ &\rightsquigarrow \langle S, E', (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A''_2 \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

where $A''_2 = \mathcal{A}_C(E[x_1 \mapsto v_1][x_2 \mapsto v_2], E')$.

It is worth noting that A'_2 is either empty or identical to $\text{Succ}(x_2 = e_2) \cap C_-$, so is A''_2 . If $A'_2 = A''_2$, everything is done.

However, what if $A'_2 \neq A''_2$? In this case, $A'_2 \subseteq A''_2 \vee A'_2 \supseteq A''_2$ holds. For now, we assume that $A'_2 \subseteq A''_2$. Since $\langle S, E', I' \rangle$ is legal, any $x' = e'$ in $A''_2 - A'_2$ satisfies $E'(x') = \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{E'}$. Eliminating such items deduces that $\langle S, E', (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A''_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S, E', (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A'_2 \rangle = \langle S, E', I' \rangle$.

As for the case when $A'_2 \supseteq A''_2$, let $\langle S'', E'', I'' \rangle$ be $\langle S, E', (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A''_2 \rangle$. Similarly, we can prove that $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle S, E', (I \cup A_1 - \{x_1 = e_1, x_2 = e_2\}) \cup A'_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S'', E'', I'' \rangle$, while $\langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S'', E'', I'' \rangle$ is proved as above.

- (c) If $x_1 \notin \text{Use}(x_2 = e_2) \wedge x_2 \in \text{Use}(x_1 = e_1)$, mimic the above proof. □

LEMMA 2.7 (CONFLUENCE). *For a legal configuration $\langle S, E, I \rangle$ of a circuit C without combinational loops, if $C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \wedge C \vdash \langle S, E, I \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle$, there exists $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ such that $\langle S_1, E_1, I_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle \wedge \langle S_2, E_2, I_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle$.*

PROOF. Theorem 2.2 indicates λ_F satisfies strong normalization, and Lemma 2.6 provides local confluence for legal configurations. The conclusion is deduced from Newman's lemma [6]. □

We can thus prove original Theorem 2.3 in our paper as follows:

THEOREM 2.8 (ORIGINAL THEOREM 2.3 IN OUR PAPER). *The steady-state reached by a circuit without combinational loops is uniquely determined:*

C has no combinational loop $\wedge C \vdash \langle S, E, C_{=} \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle \epsilon, E_1, \emptyset \rangle \wedge C \vdash \langle S, E, C_{=} \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle \epsilon, E_2, \emptyset \rangle \implies E_1 = E_2$.

PROOF. Since $\langle S, E, C_{=} \rangle$ is legal, it follows from Lemma 2.7 that there is a configuration $\langle S', E', I' \rangle$ such that $C \vdash \langle \epsilon, E_1, \emptyset \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle \wedge C \vdash \langle \epsilon, E_2, \emptyset \rangle \rightsquigarrow^* \langle S', E', I' \rangle$. However, $\langle \epsilon, E_1, \emptyset \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon, E_2, \emptyset \rangle$ are irreducible, whence $E_1 = E' = E_2$. \square

2.2 Proofs of Properties in Section 3

In this subsection, we provide complete proofs for Theorems 3.4 and 3.6 from the main paper. The proof sketches for the other theorems and lemmas in this section are already sufficiently detailed to serve as complete proofs and are therefore not repeated here.

Definition 2.9. For a non-empty $\text{Store}' \subseteq \text{Store}$ where $\langle \text{Store}', \sqsubseteq \rangle$ is a complete lattice, we call Store' a limited set of stores.

As follows, we use Store' to denote any limited set of stores.

For convenience, we introduce a generalization of synchronous flow functions:

Definition 2.10 (Fusion). We define $\text{Aff}(f)$ as $\{v \in \text{Var} \mid \exists \sigma \in \text{Store}'. \sigma(v) \neq f(\sigma)(v)\}$ for any function $f : \text{Store}' \rightarrow \text{Store}'$. For any two monotone functions $f, g : \text{Store}' \rightarrow \text{Store}'$ where $\text{Aff}(f) \cap \text{Aff}(g) = \emptyset$, we write:

$$(f * g)(x)(v) = \begin{cases} f(x)(v), & \text{if } v \in \text{Aff}(f), \\ g(x)(v), & \text{if } v \in \text{Aff}(g), \\ v, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We refer to $f * g$ as the *fusion* of f and g . The function $f * g$ is also monotone and satisfies $\text{Aff}(f * g) \subseteq \text{Aff}(f) \cup \text{Aff}(g)$.

For a finite sequence of monotone functions $f_1, \dots, f_s : \text{Store}' \rightarrow \text{Store}'$ where $\forall i, j. i \neq j \implies \text{Aff}(f_i) \cap \text{Aff}(f_j) = \emptyset$, we call the sequence a disjoint sequence of flow functions and write $f^* := f_1 * \dots * f_s$ for $f_1 * (f_2 * \dots * (f_{s-1} * f_s))$.

LEMMA 2.11. *For any disjoint sequence of flow functions $f_1, \dots, f_s : \text{Store}' \rightarrow \text{Store}'$, $\sigma \in \text{Store}'$ is a common fixed point of f_1, \dots, f_s iff it is a fixed point of $f^* = f_1 * \dots * f_s$.*

PROOF. Assume σ is a common fixed point of f_1, \dots, f_s . For any $x \in \text{Var}$, there exists at most one index j such that $x \in \text{Aff}(f_j)$. If there is no such index, $f^*(\sigma)(x) = \sigma(x)$. Otherwise, $f^*(\sigma)(x) = f_j(\sigma)(x) = \sigma(x)$. Therefore, $f^*(\sigma)(x) = \sigma(x)$ holds for any $x \in \text{Var}$, namely that $f^*(\sigma) = \sigma$.

Conversely, suppose σ is a fixed point of f^* . Notice that $f_j(\sigma)(x)$ is either $\sigma(x)$ or $f^*(\sigma)(x) = \sigma(x)$ for any index j and $x \in \text{Var}$, whence $f_j(\sigma) = \sigma$ holds for any j . \square

LEMMA 2.12. *If Store' is a complete lattice with finite height, for any disjoint sequence of flow functions $f_1, \dots, f_s : \text{Store}' \rightarrow \text{Store}'$, the functions:*

$$\begin{aligned} f^* &= f_1 * \dots * f_s, \\ f^\circ &= f_1 \circ \dots \circ f_s, \end{aligned}$$

have the same least fixed point.

PROOF. Suppose the least fixed points of f^* and f° are σ^* and σ° respectively.

On the one hand, for any $\sigma \in \mathbf{Store}'$, if $f^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma$, we have $f_i(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma$ for any index i . This implies that $f_1(f_2(\cdots(f_{n-1}(f_n(\sigma)))) \sqsubseteq f_1(f_2(\cdots(f_{n-1}(\sigma)))) \sqsubseteq \cdots \sqsubseteq f_1(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma$, whence:

$$\{\sigma \in \mathbf{Store}' \mid (f^*)(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\} \subseteq \{\sigma \in \mathbf{Store}' \mid (f^\circ)(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\}.$$

By Tarski's fixed-point theorem [8], $\sigma^* \sqsupseteq \sigma^\circ$.

On the other hand, Kleene's fixed-point theorem [2, 5] indicates that, for any monotone function $h : L \rightarrow L$, there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $h^{n+1}(\perp) = h^n(\perp)$ is the least fixed point of h . Suppose $(f^*)^m(\perp)$ and $(f^\circ)^n(\perp)$ are least fixed points of f^* and f° respectively.

Let:

$$\begin{aligned} p_n &= (f^\circ)^n(\perp), \\ q_n &= (f^*)^n(\perp). \end{aligned}$$

As the proof of Kleene's fixed-point theorem [5] demonstrates, $p_i \sqsubseteq p_{i+1}$ holds for any index i . Similarly, $q_i \sqsubseteq q_{i+1}$ also holds for any index i .

We shall prove that $p_i \sqsupseteq q_i$ for any index $i \in \mathbb{N}$ by induction:

(1) *Base Case:* From $p_0 = q_0 = \perp$, it follows that $p_0 \sqsupseteq q_0$.

(2) *Induction Step:* Assume $p_i \sqsupseteq q_i$. We shall prove $p_{i+1} \sqsupseteq q_{i+1}$.

Since $q_i \sqsubseteq q_{i+1}$, every $x \in \mathbf{Var}$ satisfies that $q_i(x) \sqsubseteq q_{i+1}(x) = (f^*)(q_i)(x)$. From the definition of f^* , it follows immediately that $q_i \sqsubseteq f_j(q_i)$ for any index $j = 1, \dots, s$.

Notice that:

$$p_{i+1} = f^\circ(p_i) \sqsupseteq f^\circ(q_i).$$

For any $x \in \mathbf{Var}$, there is at most one index j such that $x \in \text{Aff}(f_j)$. If such index does not exist, $f^\circ(q_i)(x) = q_i(x) = f^*(q_i)(x)$. Otherwise, suppose such j exists. From the assumption, it follows that:

$$f^\circ(q_i)(x) = (f_1 \circ \cdots \circ f_s)(q_i)(x) = (f_j \circ \cdots \circ f_s)(q_i)(x).$$

By $\forall j. f_j(q_i) \sqsupseteq q_i$, we have:

$$(f_j \circ \cdots \circ f_s)(q_i) \sqsupseteq (f_j \circ \cdots \circ f_{s-1})(q_i) \sqsupseteq \cdots \sqsupseteq f_j(q_i),$$

whence $(f_j \circ \cdots \circ f_s)(q_i)(x) \sqsupseteq f_j(q_i)(x) = f^*(q_i)(x)$.

Therefore, $f^\circ(q_i)(x) \sqsupseteq f^*(q_i)(x)$ holds for any $x \in \mathbf{Var}$, namely that $p_{i+1} \sqsupseteq f^\circ(q_i) \sqsupseteq f^*(q_i) = q_{i+1}$.

Let $u = \max(m, n)$, it follows that $\sigma^\circ = (f^\circ)^u(\perp) = (f^\circ)^u(\perp) \sqsupseteq (f^*)^u(\perp) = (f^*)^m(\perp) = \sigma^*$. Therefore, the least fixed points of f° and f^* are equivalent. \square

We will prove Theorem 3.4 in our paper as follows:

THEOREM 2.13 (ORIGINAL THEOREM 3.4 IN OUR PAPER). *Algorithm 1 converges to the least synchronized fixed point $\text{LSFP}_f^{C, \delta}$ if f is monotonic and $\langle L, \sqsubseteq \rangle$ is a complete lattice with finite height.*

PROOF. Since \mathbf{Var} is finite, it follows that \mathbf{Store} is also a complete lattice with finite height. Let \mathbf{Store}_δ denote $\{\sigma \in \mathbf{Store} \mid \forall v \in \mathbf{Input}_C. \sigma(v) = \delta(v)\}$, which is a limited set of stores with finite height.

Sort C_\Leftarrow into ι_1, \dots, ι_s by a reverse topological order of $G_C[C_\Leftarrow]$. By Kleene's fixed-point theorem [2, 5], Algorithm 1 computes the least fixed point of the function:

$$f[\![C_\Leftarrow]\!] \circ f[\![\iota_1]\!] \circ \cdots \circ f[\![\iota_s]\!].$$

While any element in $\text{LSFP}_f^{C,\delta}$ is a common least fixed point of $f[\llbracket C \Leftarrow \rrbracket], f[\llbracket \iota_1 \rrbracket], \dots, f[\llbracket \iota_s \rrbracket]$, which is indeed the least fixed point of $f[\llbracket C \Leftarrow \rrbracket] * f[\llbracket \iota_1 \rrbracket] * \dots * \llbracket \iota_s \rrbracket]$ by Lemma 2.11. By Lemma 2.12, Algorithm 1 computes this least fixed point. \square

We can thus prove Theorem 3.6 in our paper as follows:

THEOREM 2.14 (ORIGINAL THEOREM 3.6 IN OUR PAPER). *If $\langle L, \sqsubseteq \rangle$ is a complete lattice, $f_1 \sqsubseteq f_2$, $\sigma_1 \in \text{LSFP}_{f_1}^{C,\delta}$, and $\sigma_2 \in \text{LSFP}_{f_2}^{C,\delta}$, then $\sigma_1 \sqsubseteq \sigma_2$.*

PROOF. Since L is complete, **Store** is also a complete lattice. Let Store_δ denote $\{\sigma \in \text{Store} \mid \forall v \in \text{Input}_C. \sigma(v) = \delta(v)\}$, which is a limited set of stores.

By the assumption, $f_1^* \sqsubseteq f_2^*$. From Lemma 2.11, it follows that σ_1 is the least fixed point of f_1^* and σ_2 is that of f_2^* .

By definition, f_1^* is equal to $f_1 \llbracket C \rrbracket$. Similarly, $f_2^* = f_2 \llbracket C \rrbracket$. From $f_1 \sqsubseteq f_2$, it follows that $f_1 \llbracket C \rrbracket \sqsubseteq f_2 \llbracket C \rrbracket$. Consider any $\sigma \in \text{Store}_\delta$ which satisfies $f_2^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma$, we have:

$$f_1^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq f_1 \llbracket C \rrbracket(\sigma) \sqsubseteq f_2 \llbracket C \rrbracket(\sigma) = f_2^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma.$$

Therefore, $\{\sigma \in \text{Store}_\delta \mid f_1^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\} \supseteq \{\sigma \in \text{Store}_\delta \mid f_2^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\}$ holds.

By Tarski's fixed-point theorem [8],

$$\sigma_1 = \sqcap \{\sigma \in \text{Store}_\delta \mid f_1^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\} \sqsubseteq \sqcap \{\sigma \in \text{Store}_\delta \mid f_2^*(\sigma) \sqsubseteq \sigma\} = \sigma_2.$$

\square

3 Discussion: Chaotic Values

In our main paper (Definition 2.1), we chose **Value** = \mathbb{Z} (i.e., the set of mathematical integers) purely for ease of understanding and presentation. A more rigorous and complete treatment of values is as follows:

$$\text{Value} := \mathbb{Z} \cup \mathbb{Z}' \quad \text{where} \quad \mathbb{Z}' := \{i' \mid i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

Here, each i' represents a random value drawn from $E_{\text{rand}} : \text{Var} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}'$ in the initial configuration $c_0 = \langle S_0, E_{\text{rand}}, C_\Leftarrow \rangle$, modeling the non-deterministic behavior of real-world digital circuits at power-up. We refer to such values as *chaotic values* to reflect their physical meaning.

The definition of evaluation (original Definition 2.9 in our paper) requires only a slight refinement, as defined case by case below, which preserves the overall structure and spirit of the original semantics:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket n \rrbracket_E &:= n & \llbracket y \rrbracket_E &:= E(y) \\ \llbracket y \text{ op } z \rrbracket_E &:= \begin{cases} \mathfrak{C}(\mathfrak{Z}(E(y)) \text{ op } \mathfrak{Z}(E(z))) & \text{if } E(y) \in \mathbb{Z}' \vee E(z) \in \mathbb{Z}', \\ E(y) \text{ op } E(z) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \\ \llbracket \text{mux}(w, y, z) \rrbracket_E &:= \begin{cases} \mathfrak{C}(E(y)) \text{ if } E(w) \neq 0' \wedge E(w) \in \mathbb{Z}', & \mathfrak{C}(E(z)) \text{ if } E(w) = 0', \\ E(y) \text{ if } E(w) \neq 0 \wedge E(w) \notin \mathbb{Z}', & E(z) \text{ if } E(w) = 0. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\mathfrak{Z}(x) := \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ i, & \text{if } x = i' \in \mathbb{Z}'. \end{cases} \quad \mathfrak{C}(x) := \begin{cases} x', & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ x, & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{Z}'. \end{cases}$$

From a programming language perspective, chaotic values should be treated as undefined, as they are not explicitly set by the developer. Thus, in our analysis, we over-approximate such values using \perp .

Definition 3.1 (Abstraction Function for Chaotic Values). For any chaotic value $i' \in \mathbb{Z}'$, the abstraction function $\alpha : \mathbb{Z}' \rightarrow L$ is defined as $\alpha(i') := \perp$.

Based on the hardware-specific treatment of chaotic values, we state the following lemma, which ensures one of the soundness preconditions required by Theorem 3.5 in our main paper.

LEMMA 3.2 (OVER-APPROXIMATION OF INITIAL STORE OVER INITIAL CONFIGURATION). *Let $\sigma_0 = \delta \sqcup \{_ \mapsto \perp\}$ be the initial store derived from a stimulus description δ , and let $c_0 = \langle S_0, E_{\text{rand}}, C_{=} \rangle$ be the initial configuration. Then $\alpha(c_0) \sqsubseteq \sigma_0$.*

PROOF. By Definition 3.1 above and Definition 3.1 in our main paper, we have $\alpha(c_0) = \alpha(E_{\text{rand}}) = \{_ \mapsto \perp\} \sqsubseteq \delta \sqcup \{_ \mapsto \perp\} = \sigma_0$. \square

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